

Enhancing critical thinking to foster students' analytical capacity in academic writing

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The current qualitative study aimed at fostering critical thinking skills in students and enhancing their analytical capacity, leading them to generate critical academic writing. An open-ended questionnaire dealing with lecturers' expertise and experiences in teaching writing and the role of their critical thinking skills in writing itself was administered to eight lecturers with expertise in teaching writing. The obtained data were submitted to manual coding, and the findings showed that fostering critical thinking in student writers should follow a stepwise process, whereby they learn to (a) interpret, (b) analyze, (c) synthesize, (d) evaluate, and (e) reflect. It was concluded that problem-based learning is the optimal approach to enhance critical thinking among student writers of academic texts.

Keywords: Academic Writing; Analytical Capacity; Composing Skills; Critical Thinking; Second Language Writing

1. Introduction

Writing is a product of thinking and is often (a) produced in response to an issue, (b) engaged to provide some analysis, or (c) utilized to offer some perspective. As a result of logical thinking, writing should be able to reflect that kind of thinking to deliver a systematic and rational understanding (Pei et al., 2017).

This means that one of the 'affordances' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b) of deep thinking is to make qualified writing possible. Deep thinking requires that writing be supported by high thinking capacity; to write critically, writers need (a) critical thinking skills, (b) width of knowledge, and (c) depth of analysis. As such, critical writing is a form of writing that is based on the mental capacity to critically read and describe the phenomenon at hand; critical writing occurs as

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a result of critical thinking, and critical thinking affects writers' capacity to analyze and discuss.

Critical thinking is the main pedestal upon which writing stands. Through critical thinking, deep analysis can be achieved. Thorndahl and Stentoft (2020) define critical thinking as a sociocultural practice that occurs among people in specific situations. It is a reciprocal, agentic, and shared responsibility, and is not solely dependent on individual abilities; rather, it is also influenced by collective, institutional, and organizational circumstances. It is a lens through which reality is viewed, and with which reality will be read and analyzed (Thorndahl & Stentoft, 2020).

Critical thinking in writing can be considered as a scalpel of analysis in illustrating reality, giving meanings and discussions to reality from different perspectives. It is the flexible, contextual manner used for describing, discussing, and generating perspectives in dealing with an issue. Toshpulatova and Kinjemuratova (2020) refer to critical thinking as learners' ability to grasp ideas through self-reflection on the way in which one learns and discovers solutions to an issue based on viewpoints from various angles. This means that, when critical thinking is wielded to seek the solution to a problem, self-reflection and discovery should be applied to the problem. In connection to writing, critical thinking can be viewed as the mental framework through which one will be able to convert abstract ideas of the mind into concrete written texts. In line with this, Padmanabha (2018) argued that critical thinking is a disciplined, self-monitored, self-directed, and self-corrective way or habit of thinking. It is integrated in terms of clarity, relevance, logical soundness, and specific goals and objectives. This view supposes that there should be self-capacity in presenting fact as a problem, displaying analysis and perspective.

Academic writing, commonly taught to students in higher education (Eckstein et al., 2023; Hernandez, 2023; Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b), needs to be enhanced and scaffolded by critical thinking because this helps students (a) search for problems, (b) formulate a research problem to solve, (c) elaborate on data and facts, (d) display related literature, (e) present analyses, (f) generate a new perspective toward the problem faced (Sánchez & Chapetón, 2021) and simultaneously develop their own creativity (Salmani Nodoushan, 2018, 2023a). Therefore, critical thinking skills in academic writing assist students in enlarging their points of view on how to position themselves as thinkers. The wider the range of perspectives they are able to demonstrate in their writing, the more effectively they have used critical thinking skills in formulating and mapping a problem or issue. Critical thinking in academic writing activities trains the mind to be able to be responsive to the

environment as a social fact to criticize and discuss in a written text (Padmanabha, 2018).

Academic writing deals with the way in which learners state the general and thesis statement in the introductory paragraph, followed by the body of the essay, and ending with a concluding paragraph. Furthermore, the abstract, introduction (problem statement, purpose statement), method, findings, results, discussion and suggestions, references and citation section, linguistic and stylistic features, ethical principles and formal features are all characteristics of academic writing that must be included (Akkaya & Aydin, 2018). Academic writing should be taught initially by scaffolding writing assignments and providing clear assignment criteria. This enables students to understand both objective and subjective writing tasks (Campbell, 2019). Consequently, the learners learn the principles of academic writing so that they can achieve the goal.

It is on this ground that the current qualitative study has sought to show if and how the teaching of critical thinking skills can foster in students the analytical capacity they need for generating critical academic writing outputs.

2. Background

2.1. Critical thinking

Critical thinking is defined as a skill used (a) to interrogate, (b) to recognize and test previously held suppositions, (c) to perceive ambiguity, (d) to inspect, interpret, assess, reason, and reflect, (e) to settle judgments and choices, and (f) to clarify, express, and legitimize positions (Akdağ & Kirkgöz, 2020). A learner is considered to have critical thinking skills when he is able to question, process all of the available information, debate, reason, and make rational judgments, as well as generating a new perspective toward an issue. This view is supported by Özelçi and Çalışkan (2019), who state that critical thinking skills enhance individuals' ability to understand and make sense of the world, as well as events and situations around them. Individuals need to see and respond to a phenomenon so that they can build the concept and debate the data displayed.

Because critical thinking skills relate to the way in which an individual can use his knowledge in processing the data, critical thinking is defined as the set of skills and dispositions which enable one to solve problems logically and to attempt to reflect autonomously (Gotoh, 2017). In critical thinking skills, the individual is required to be independent in interacting with the issue and to be able to question, debate, provide reasoning, and reflect as a result of the thinking process.

Tseng (2019) and Lam (2020) propose concept mapping activities to enhance critical thinking skills. Concept mapping is beneficial to help individuals to sharpen and strengthen their critical thinking skills. Critical thinking is defined here as the process of self-regulatory judgment resulting in interpretation, analysis, evaluation, and inference; an explanation of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criterion logical, and contextual considerations should be viewed as part of the concept mapping process. As such, the steps of interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, and explanation are viewed as the core skills of critical thinking; this means that concept mapping is helpful to operationalize the implementation of critical thinking skills.

In line with this, it is necessary for individuals to use their critical thinking skills through active learning. In this approach, a learning environment must enable learners to enhance their cognitive skills and gain knowledge while they are learning content and language (Kusumoto, 2018). Therefore, critical thinking is purposeful, reasoned, and goal-directed because it involves solving problems, formulating inferences, calculating likelihoods, and making decisions. When people think critically, they evaluate the outcomes of their thought processes and evaluate decisions and solutions (Hasnunidah et al., 2020; Tahira & Haider, 2019; Yükselir, 2020).

2.2. Academic Writing

Writing skills cannot be learnt without the aid of reading skills; to learn to write, students need to read and understand text books that teach them the 'learning strategies', à la Nemati et al. (2010), that they need in learning how to write. Moreover, they need the support of competent writing teachers who often resort to (1) 'remedial instruction' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021c) in their teaching practices, (2) correct approaches to 'error treatment' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007a), (3) unbiased evaluation techniques (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021b), and, most importantly, (4) fostering critical thinking and creativity in their students (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2016, 2018).

To write in an academic style requires the skill to be able to demonstrate familiarity with the rhetorical conventions and social understandings of the community of practice, and observe suitable patterns of social and rhetorical interactions. For example, EFL students need to learn to differentiate between 'meaning' and 'intention' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007b, 2021a, 2022), and to know that any written text, in addition to expressing certain types of meaning, needs to also achieve some generic or discursive intention (e.g., enumeration, definition, persuasion, argumentation, etc.).

The arguments made in any written text should be both acceptable and convincing; research claims must be framed to project appropriate certainty and maximum plausibility. Moreover, vigorous argument should explain the

originality of the claims (Hyland & Jiang, 2017; Langum & Sullivan, 2017; McKinley & Rose, 2019; Stapleton, 2019; Xie, 2020). Therefore, the teaching of academic writing should pay attention to multilingual and multicultural contexts so that learners can use these contexts to write. Academic writing in different contexts is comprehended as the effort to be able to position the learners' point of view in presenting the issue, discussing and interpreting it through the evidence and references used.

Language teaching should be based on the learners' backgrounds to facilitate their understanding which can help them gain a deeper knowledge and finally reach creativity in their profession (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018); the same is true when learning to write. By considering this, the way to write academic texts will be contextualized. The key approaches used in the teaching of academic writing are a focus on writers and their cognitive processes, on the text and its linguistic forms and patterns, on the discourse community and its practices and conventions, and the first language of the writer and its differences from the target language (Allahverdi et al., 2023; Burgess & Pallant, 2013; Cumming, Lai, & Cho, 2016). Therefore, for academic writing, the learners are required to focus on what to write, what to present, and what to claim and counterclaim, based on evidence as well as data.

In academic writing, it is critical that students learn to present their arguments in a logical order and to arrive at conclusions. They should always interact with other texts, so that there will be frequent references to the ideas, thinking or research of other authors (Khazaal, 2019). Their writing must be characterized by evidence-based arguments, precise word choice, logical organization, and an impersonal tone. A distinct style of expression is used by researchers to define the intellectual boundaries of their disciplines and their specific areas of expertise. Learners must consider the following features of academic writing to make their own writing acceptable: (1) evidence-based referencing and citations; (2) appropriate structure; (3) clear organization; (4) demonstration of critical reading, writing, and thinking; and (5) an appropriate written style (Khazaal, 2019; Valdes, 2019).

3. Method

This study uses the qualitative research design. the researcher describes the phenomena that the participants experience. The researcher's role is to determine how the phenomena should be observed and recorded and then analyzed to afford the themes that they hide.

In qualitative research designs, all data are meaningful and can make contributions toward interpreting the phenomena. Corpora are collected through a series of different techniques (including structured or unstructured interviews with informants) and are then narrated using a qualitative data

approach; as such, the current study positions each phenomenon as a fact. The qualitative research approach used in this study enables the researchers—keeping an eye on the research goal—to display and present the phenomena as naturally as possible.

3.1. Participants

The participants in this research comprise eight English lecturers ($N = 8$) from eight universities in Indonesia: (1) Universitas Merdeka Pasuruan, (2) Universitas Negeri Surabaya, (3) Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Blitar, (4) Universitas Tadulako, (5) Rajamangala University of Technology Krungthep, (6) Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidoarjo, (7) STKIP Bina Insan Mandiri, and (8) Universitas Muhammadiyah Jember. All of the participants have expertise in interpreting critical thinking and academic writing, based on their long-term experiences as English teachers. Their experiences in viewing and comprehending critical thinking and academic writing are the source of the data for this qualitative research work.

3.2. Instruments

The instrument used to obtain the data for this qualitative research was an open-ended questionnaire. The questions in the questionnaire dealt with the (1) importance of critical thinking skills, (2) the relationship between critical thinking skills and writing, and (3) critical thinking skills in academic writing. They required the respondents to present their own personal definitions of critical thinking and to reflect on the importance of critical thinking in language teaching classrooms.

3.3. Procedure

The data obtained from the questionnaire were analyzed through manual coding by searching for patterns in the data to organize and group similarly coded data into categories (cf. Saldaña, 2013). Every item of data obtained from the questionnaire results was coded based on the research problem proposed—that is, (1) if and (2) how the teaching of critical thinking skills can foster in students the analytical capacity they need for generating critical academic writing outputs.

4. Results

The examples in italics (below) illustrate how each respondent defines thinking skills as the independent variable contributing to students' academic writing. It is claimed that the use of critical thinking skills will enhance the students' analytical capacity whereby empowering them to engage in better academic writing.

The respondents' way of viewing critical thinking skills and their connection to writing is reflected in the different perspectives they have presented in their responses to the open-ended questionnaire. However, their understanding, either in theory or practice, of critical thinking skills and their connection to academic writing shows that all of the respondents have tried to adequately instruct the students in writing during their writing activities. Based on their experience, they argued that analytical capacity should be enhanced through critical thinking skills, and that this is of benefit their students' writings. The emerging themes from the qualitative data of this study show that the main reason for using critical thinking skills to foster students' analytical capacity is for producing well-written critical academic papers. Nevertheless, the eight respondents had different views on defining and practicing critical thinking skills in academic writing. The first respondent said:

Critical thinking in my opinion is the ability to skillfully conceptualize, apply, analyze, synthesize, and evaluate information. Having this ability facilitates the students in processing the information and knowledge, so that they know what to do and to write. Consequently, when composing a text consisting of an introductory paragraph, body of text, and a concluding paragraph, the students will start from the thesis statement and detailed analysis in the text. In order to create well-established critical thinking skills, it is necessary to consider how best to teach these skills to students. Determining the learning objective is taught through questioning, practice, review, refinement, and improvement. In detail, to foster critical thinking, teachers should promote or encourage questions from students through a problem-solving method of teaching, and they can encourage cooperative and collaborative learning among student groups.

The second respondent viewed critical thinking skills as:

... the ability to adapt (adjust actions and strategies to accomplish tasks), examine (use a variety of methods to explore and to analyze), create (use one's knowledge and imagination to express new and innovative ideas), communicate (use clear language to express one's ideas and to share information), collaborate (work with others to achieve better outcomes), inquire (seek information that excites one's curiosity and inspires one's learning), link (apply knowledge to reach new understandings), reflect (review one's thoughts and experiences to guide one's actions), and strive (use effort and determination to focus on challenging tasks). To enhance students' critical thinking skills in academic writing, teachers should become role models in teaching-learning activities to reach the purpose of academic writing.

The third respondent called critical thinking skills "*the ability to evaluate things logically and offer details supported by critical reasoning*", and emphasized the

need to “*stimulate students to solve a task that needs critical skills; for example, by asking them to synthesize information from more than one source.*” The respondent’s strategy for teaching critical thinking skills is to “*ask students to write an argument and give reasons behind their argument, and to make comments on certain issues.*”

The fourth respondent categorized critical thinking skills as the ability to:

. . . inquire (seek new information), link (apply knowledge to reach understandings), and reflect (review experiences). In critical thinking activities, students need those as the effort to be able to write. Therefore, when students are familiar with those, it will be easy for them in writing. Qualified academic writing will be manifest when the students have been able to use these steps of thinking in processing the information and knowledge.

The fifth respondent illustrated critical thinking skills as:

. . . the effort to tap into students’ knowledge about how to develop new ideas clearly by giving basic assumptions, asking them to try reversing things, and asking them to evaluate the evidence. The final project requires that students use all of them in composing a text. This is a practical method in teaching critical thinking skills in academic writing.

The sixth respondent described critical thinking skills as:

. . . the ability to create innovations. Students are expected to be active in responding to the issue and give a detailed analysis of the issue. In teaching critical thinking skills through academic writing, it is important to provide a good method and curriculum in which the teachers are required to link all of the issues with the students’ life experiences.

The seventh respondent explained critical thinking skills as:

. . . a thinking process gathered from, or generated by, observation, experience, reflection, reasoning, or communication. Through these steps, students can select and differentiate the right information. The process of teaching these skills in writing involves giving students some narrative texts, then discussing them together or asking the learners to summarize the text and give responses.

Finally, the eighth respondent interpreted critical thinking skills as:

. . . the ability to analyze and evaluate an issue. The teaching strategy that can be used in teaching critical thinking skills is to give the students some problems, asking them to solve them, or to explain an issue from a different point of view, then practicing this in their writing.

5. Discussion

Fostering in students the critical thinking skills that they need in academic writing supports the outcomes of the learning objective. When the students' writing is enhanced through critical thinking skills, it helps them to design their perspectives in reading, analyzing, and delivering their thoughts. It is important to say that critical thinking skills are the tool used to map the situation on the current issue. Because of the critical thinking skills used, the students are able to arrange and formulate their ideas into the written text.

The findings of the current study lend support to claims made by Salmani Nodoushan (2016) who argues that the learners' ability in writing should be enhanced with logical reasoning, objective argumentation, and critical thinking. As such, qualified writing is the process (a) of using thinking based on reasoning, and (b) of knowing what to think about and write. Therefore, critical thinking in writing has the role of shaping the students' mindsets so that they are keen to discuss and write about the issue.

The findings of this study also lend support to another perspective on writing; students should be able to use the cognitive approach of "revision" to answer their problems in writing activities. This means that qualified writing always starts from the students' anxieties to review their writings, predicting the problems they might have and the possible actions they may take towards their writing. It is a challenge for students to do their best in writing activities. Likewise, Rezaee and Mubarak (2018) have opined that the promotion of critical thinking skills will positively affect students' ability to acquire the new language and their proficiency; the students' ability in writing shows better performance so that they know what to say, what/how to think, and what to write in their writing activities.

Therefore, the goal of writing is not only to deal with what is produced in written form but also to give meanings to and perspective on the text. The writer is an agent with agentive affordances that enable him/her to inject meaning from outside into the texts he/she produces (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a, 2022). Because critical thinking skills start from the 'verbs' (a) to conceptualize, (b) to apply, (c) to analyze, (d) to synthesize, and (e) to evaluate, it is important to empower learners with these skills to empower them for the processing of information and responding to the issues they face. It is expected that the students will be able to bring their critical thinking skills to bear on the processing of information which can then be presented/narrated in a well-organized written text consisting of an introductory paragraph, a body, and a concluding paragraph—i.e., a five-paragraph essay (cf. Imaniar et al., 2018). In other words, critical thinking skills, à la the respondents in this study, contribute to defining the issue to write about.

With the critical thinking skills that they possess and engage in writing, students can systematically arrange and organize their ideas in the text. In other words, critical thinking skills function as the framework that can be utilized in writing—i.e., in searching the topic, defining the research problem, analyzing the research problem with all supporting data and evidence, reflecting, and evaluating. Principally, critical thinking skills scaffold the students in mapping the issue to be discussed in written form and in detail. As the participants in this study have suggested, the goal of critical thinking skills is to trigger students to think and compose their thoughts in deep analysis (cf. Bennett, 2018; Hanim et al., 2020).

It is important to say that critical thinking skills in writing should be trained continuously to make the students habituated to de facto and automatic critical thinking; the use of critical thinking skills in writing needs to become a subconscious habit for students so that they will approach every issue critically. Empowered with critical thinking skills, they will question why problems appear and how they can be tackled. This then motivates and inspires them to research and obtain all of the relevant information necessary to process the supporting data and to evidence them in their discussions. Therefore, critical thinking skills in academic writing actually guide the students either directly or indirectly to think openly, fairly, and honestly about what to think, what to do, and what to write (cf. Kabataş et al., 2020).

This means that critical thinking skills in writing become an effective instrument scaffolding the students with a thought framework that they can use in formulating their thoughts and writing about them. Critical thinking skills drive students to apply their knowledge effectively in a written text (Ahmed, 2018). According to the participants in this study, critical thinking skills (a) help students in finding their way in writing and (b) enable them to write based on a targeted goal. Consequently, such skills not only function as a thought framework but also clarify and cleanse the concepts that are to be written about/on. This lends support to Schicker (2018), who argued that critical thinking enriches the genre approach to writing by improving students' stylistic, textual, and grammatical skills (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2012) while also increasing their ability to think critically about their own language acquisition process. Through critical thinking skills, à la the respondents, students expand their cultural awareness (cf. Dabbagh et al., 2023) and can practice their social skills when negotiating the meanings of genres.

Another theme that emerged from the data of this study was that writing teachers can foster in their students the critical thinking skills that they need. In order to teach critical thinking effectively through academic writing, problem-based teaching is, à la the respondents, the most effective option. Students write based on issues that are intended to widen their knowledge and

experiences. The problem-based teaching approach is effective in educating and teaching students to be active participants in any chosen activity. Their abilities will be sharpened and trained so that they can do better in their writing activities. It is important that the problem-based be the chosen approach by teachers who aim to facilitate students' understanding of their writing activities.

According to the respondents, the problem-based approach is the preferred way to help students get closer to realities. This supports Sari et al. (2020), who argued that a problem-based learning approach supports the students in their writing process and other learning activities. In this connection, the ability to 'analyze' is one important factor contributing to students' success in collecting the data used to give argumentation and logical reasoning. This is a major benefit of problem-based learning, and it helps the students in their writing. According to the respondents, students' data-driven writing that employs data analysis makes it possible for their ideas to be processed well and filtered neatly since it brings academic writing traits to bear on the task. Academic writing traits include (a) scanning research texts, (b) note-taking and summarizing skills, (c) synthesizing material from a variety of sources, (d) understanding of ethics in writing and the avoidance of plagiarism, (e) in-text citations and referencing standards, and (f) aptitude in organizing and laying out written text, tables, figures and other elements of a manuscript (cf. Çelik, 2020). When writing academic texts, students should pay attention to these traits and conventions. This means that employing critical thinking skills while writing academic texts may facilitate the use of an academic written style, or genre (cf. Boginskaya, 2022).

Qualified writing, according to the participants in this study, is one that engages any knowledge and experiences that are relevant and support and strengthen students' arguments. Nevertheless, students should be guided in formulating their thoughts, and in implementing interpretation, analysis, interference, evaluation, explanation, and self-regulation. These stages are to be applied in writing activities. As said before, the default organization of academic writing comprises three sections (i.e., 'introduction', 'development', and 'conclusion'), and each section requires the writer's ability to think critically (cf. Dewi, 2015).

This means that students should become familiarized with using these steps. The steps of teaching critical thinking through writing can begin with (1) defining the research problem, and (2) determining what to write. Students can be asked to discuss the research problems that should be addressed, and this requires (3) extensive reading about/on the issue at hand. This is then followed by (4) interpretation, (5) analysis, (6) interference, (7) evaluation, (8) explanation, and (9) self-regulation. The teacher can facilitate the students'

task by teaching them how to explore their knowledge and experiences so that they can compose an acceptable text (cf. Jumariati & Sulisty, 2017; Kabataş et al., 2020).

When the students are able to employ critical thinking in the right way, it will contribute to their analytical capacity so that they can write (a) well and (b) in a systematic and reasonably organized manner. All in all, the participants in this study have agreed that students' ability in writing academically should be supported by critical thinking skills which can improve the quality of their written performance. The writing process in academic texts always relates to the management of data collection and this will be successful when students have the ability to manage the data well, an ability that does not come from scratch, but requires active teaching and hands-on experience. The major known facts are that (a) critical thinking skills help all students in their writing, and that (b) the teaching strategies to be engaged in implanting critical thinking skills in the teaching of the writing skill are 'problem solving' and 'collaboration'.

6. Conclusion

Critical thinking has the role of scaffolding students to explore their knowledge and experience. Through critical thinking, students have the freedom to identify the issue, interpret it and analyze it, by comparing and contrasting it with relevant resources; they can and reflect on and value it in an effort to generate a new perspective on existing problems. With this, students can write about their thoughts in academic texts and organize their thoughts in an orderly manner. Writing itself is a thinking process, and no text can come about in the absence of thought. Through writing, students think and produce a written thought. To conclude, the writing process is the same as the critical thinking process, but in writing, students discuss an issue or a research problem in a written text.

Based on the experiences of the participants in this study, it can be concluded that critical thinking skills in academic writing support the students' writing activities because such skills equip students with a tool that is meaningful and useful for their mindsets. Writing needs to be supported by critical thinking skills that can affect the students' achievement and performance in their academic writing. Critical thinking skills that are enhanced in and through academic writing contribute to the students' writing performance. To sum up, critical thinking skills and academic writing are interrelated and work in tandem; high quality academic writing should be assessed according to how student writers use critical thinking in their written texts.

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